

THE UNIVERSITY AS A BRAIN FOR MANAGERS: HIGHER EDUCATION AND UNIVERSITY AUTONOMY

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Abstract

The complexity of Federal Higher Education Institutions (FHEI) is a peculiar feature of these institutions. The objective of this paper is to identify the main challenges for university autonomy to be respected in IFES. To this end, a University metaphor was seen as a brain and the challenges of its managers. It was concluded that the manager, together with the community must fight for autonomy, in addition to the pursuit of rights being respected.

Keywords: Autonomy. Education. Managers. University.

Introduction

Federal Institutions of Higher Education (IFES), as Morgan (1996) states, are organizations where information, knowledge and learning are key resources, being the inspiration of a living brain, capable of learning and having ideas. The university has as its basic activities, teaching, research and extension, which, in turn, require directors for each division, such as directors, sub-directors, departments, colleges, schools, etc. Such activities also refer the image of a brain and its subdivisions to its proper functioning.

Universities are complex institutions, due to the activities they carry out and the diversity of staff working as their servers, professors, students and their role in society. Along with all this complexity, the IFES still face several challenges such as aspects related to the budget, struggle for its university autonomy, devaluation by governments and legal requirements and rules from regulatory entities.

This study was developed from Gareth Morgan's presentation of the idea of organizations seen as brains. After that, an approach to the management of federal institutions of higher education as a brain will be carried out, according to their structure and their leaders. The conclusion seeks to return to the statement, understand the organization of the IFES and emphasize the importance of university autonomy.

Theoretical Reference

2.1. Management of Educational Institutions and Current Legislation

The Law of Guidelines and Bases of Brazilian Education (LDB 9394/96) is the legislation that regulates the Brazilian educational system, whether public or private, covering basic education to higher education.

Article 1 of the Law of Guidelines and Bases of National Education (2017) states that “education encompasses the training processes that develop in family life, in human coexistence, at work, in teaching and research institutions, in social movements and civil society organizations and cultural events”.

According to the LDB, school education is predominantly developed through teaching, in their own institutions. In this sense, education is everyone's right, from basic education to higher education. However, in practice, there is a social inequality for the admission, permanence and completion of graduation of several students.

In view of the inequalities present in higher education, the manager responsible for any educational institution must be aware of the legislation, seeking fair methods that guarantee the permanence of the student until the conclusion of their course. Goal 19 of the PNE 2014/2024 cites the

"democratic management of education to ensure conditions, within two years, for the effective democratic management of education, associated with technical criteria of merit and performance and public consultation with the school community, within the scope of public schools, providing resources and technical support of the Union to do so”.

Thus, the manager must make their decisions guided by pedagogical criteria, providing improvements for the teaching-learning process, and the smooth running of the school. Vaz (2008) reports that the fundamental activities for management must be considered together, to deliver to the target audience a better quality of the product or service.

Betlinski (2013) proposes to integrate individual goals (of the worker) and business goals, focusing on a more participative and innovative management. From this perspective, the manager must be aware of his posture and the pedagogical political project. This political pedagogical project must be seen as an ongoing and adaptive process and not just a legal obligation.

Kaufmann (2014, p. 39), reports that "the constant changes that have been taking place in the world today demand from the manager a profile that is more open to new ideas, aimed at the participation of all." The author also warns that “for this, one of the fundamental characteristics for the participatory process is what refers to the issue of leadership”. And he goes on to emphasize that “the manager must be a leader, attentive to administrative, pedagogical and interpersonal relationship issues” (KAUFMANN, 2014, p. 39).

At a time when the management is successful, the gains are not only for the individual who holds the position, but for the entire community involved, with parents, staff and teachers in a harmonious relationship, aiming at the effective academic and civic education of today's students, which represent the future of the nation. In the case of IFES, such gains depend on university autonomy and its prerogatives.

2.2. The Autonomy of Federal Institutions of Higher Education

The university autonomy included in the Federal Constitution of 1988 has been generating debates about the role of the university, as this concept is not legally clear, particularly with regard to public law entities. Autonomy is based on the fundamental activities of the university: teaching, research and extension.

In its article 207, the Federal Constitution guarantees that “universities enjoy didactic-scientific, administrative, financial and asset management autonomy, and will obey the principle of inseparability between teaching, research and extension”. Thus, the defense of university autonomy and all its achievements for the institutions becomes fundamental.

However, the expansion of higher education did not keep pace with legislation. The biggest concern of universities is related to administrative autonomy, such as the financial, budget and hiring aspects, through restrictions imposed by decrees.

Figure 1 – The University, considering the autonomy and its limits in CF and also the principle of inseparability between teaching, research and extension. Source: own author (2019).

The self-explanatory precept of the text of the Constitution, generates interpretations that its regulation is not necessary. Even with the recognition that the university must have the

freedom to walk by itself, determining its curricula, research, courses, in addition to its internal regulations, university autonomy was controlled several times by legal measures.

The Ministry of Education, as it has great regulatory power, controls the regulation and accreditation of courses, sets salaries and remuneration, so that autonomy does not actually occur. The laws served to mold university autonomy to political and economic interests, in different periods. Thus indicating that they were used to direct autonomy according to the purposes of certain groups and reinforce the tutelage of governments (AMARAL, 2018).

Autonomy creates mechanisms for the university to learn to walk by itself, to find its own paths, without waiting for everything to be determined by a legal instrument. Thus, autonomy is not restricted to a norm but expands its limits within university campuses. It is an autonomy built by the action of professors-researchers, employees and students.

The efficiency of university autonomy is only present when the tripod professors-technicians-students is followed. However, the level of representation is often not obeyed in most HEIs, where the number of student representatives is lower when compared to professors and technicians. The collegiate bodies must maintain a representative number with greater equality among the members of the aforementioned tripod, which in turn is not respected.

Even with the representativeness of the members, university autonomy does not mean independence. The university is an entity of public administration, being subject to the laws and constitutional principles of public administration. The hallmark of autonomy is the importance of recognizing the university's autonomy, as it does not belong to any government (AMARAL, 2018).

The norms currently in force already guarantee the entire autonomy of the university, but the university community must fight against government interference in the processes internal to the university (FÁVERO, 2000). Managers of higher education institutions must seek unity to face the actions of governments that seek to weaken autonomy.

The exercise of academic, administrative, financial and asset management autonomy does not constitute a means for the university to make or hide mistakes, crises and shortages, but an important advance in the necessary dimensions. Thus, it is extremely important for managers and the university community to seek rights so that autonomy is fully fulfilled.

Autonomy increases political responsibility for decisions, the internalization of the culture of planning and management efficiency, and the challenge of articulating academic quality, focus on merit, with social commitment, focus on inclusion, and economic commitment, focus in technological innovation.

Democratic management needs to be a priority in the construction of university autonomy. The expansion or reduction of university autonomy does not depend exclusively on an external law, but rather, is directly related to the political action of professors, administrative employees and students of each institution. This means that if we want a more autonomous university, we have to fight politically for it.

Discussions

The fight for university autonomy occurs when its leaders have managerial skills and knowledge to deal with different situations in the current scenario. However, it is very common that professors who assume positions of directors of academic units, pro-rector departments or even the rector, do not have such knowledge. This lack of knowledge related to management can influence this struggle for university autonomy, thus affecting the daily activities and services provided by the institution.

Factors such as the time available for job activities, the number of meetings and events that require the presence of an officer; the number of ordinances to be read; and everyday emergency actions are some of the challenges that a manager may face during his or her time in the position. The division of tasks and the participation of the entire team and community is extremely important for the development of the University.

The lack of prior knowledge about the function and management aspects, the relational divergences of subordinates, administrative and personnel are also added to the main adversities of the new IFES managers, especially those of universities. The professors who take on positions related to management are faced with the absence of information from past administrations, which makes their work more difficult. These aspects must be rethought in order for the scenario to be changed. With the aforementioned adversities and based on the metaphor of the brain, the vision of autonomy can be wounded when such impasses are resolved.

Conclusões

O cargo de gestor exige conhecer e executar processos de avaliação institucional e de desempenho dos servidores, e a criação de políticas para o ingresso, permanência e conclusão de curso dos discentes. Conforme Morgan (1996), deve-se “iniciar ações corretivas quando discrepâncias forem detectadas” para evitar um feedback negativo, como no momento de assumir o cargo e ao longo de toda a sua passagem. Assim como um cérebro que aprende em todos os momentos e situações, o gestor visto também como uma parte do cérebro da universidade, deve manter-se aberto para formação e capacitações para tal cargo.

Mesmo que o novo gestor já possua experiências ligadas a direção na universidade, é preciso ter em mente que cada momento é único, o cargo ocupado pode estar em um grau de hierarquia maior e a equipe nem sempre é a mesma. Saber conviver com as divergências é um fator fundamental para o sucesso da instituição. Pode-se dizer que se o gestor não tenha uma postura adequada ou não saiba dirigir corretamente a sua unidade, na analogia feita com o cérebro, seria como se esse órgão tivesse com um ponto central falho, podendo gerar problemas em outras funções do corpo, mesmo que não seja próxima do sistema nervoso. Dessarte, mesmo que a direção não sofra com interferências de uma má gestão, algum servidor ou aluno poderá ter algum serviço defasado.

A gestão tida como o cérebro da universidade, terá meios para comandar as outras funções do organismo, exercendo ligações com os diversos setores e proporcionando um ensino de qualidade. Importante lembrar que, assim como o cérebro trabalha em conjunto com os demais órgãos e sistemas, a gestão universitária não trabalha sozinha. Os gestores universitários no exercício de sua função, devem buscar a gestão democrática e participativa, auxiliando os

gestores e as IFES a melhorarem seus processos de planejamento e acompanhamento desses profissionais e nas atividades cotidianas.

A metáfora utilizando o cérebro e a inteligência é um ponto chave para os gestores universitários. Ao mesmo tempo que a gestão é vista como o cérebro pela universidade, devido a sua grande importância para o desenvolvimento da instituição, torna-se necessário também que exista a inteligência. Essa inteligência pode ser vista de duas formas: a primeira no sentido de o dirigente adotar a gestão democrática e participativa, obtendo assim melhores resultados para a própria IFES, e a segunda, no sentido de o próprio docente buscar capacitação para o cargo de gestão assumido, buscando conhecimentos e estudos ausentes em sua formação que são essenciais para o exercício de tal função e garantir a autonomia universitária.

Referências Bibliográficas

AMARAL, Nelson Cardoso. Autonomia e financiamento das IFES: desafios e ações. Avaliação, Campinas; Sorocaba, SP, v. 13, n. 3, p. 647-680, nov. 2008.

BETLINSKI, Carlos. Práticas e Perspectivas de Democracia na Gestão Educacional. São Paulo: Paulus, 2013.

FÁVERO, Maria de Lourdes A. Autonomia universitária mais uma vez: subsídios para o debate. In: SGUISSARDI, Valdemar (Org.). Educação superior: velhos e novos desafios. São Paulo: Xamã, p. 179-196. 2000.

FEDERAL, Supremo Tribunal et al. Constituição da República Federativa do Brasil. Supremo Tribunal Federal, 1988.

KAUFMANN, C. Barreiras de uma gestão democrática: Dificuldades encontradas para que a Democracia se consolide na gestão. Unoesc & Ciência – ACHS, Joaçaba, v. 5, n. 1, p. 33-42, jan./jun. 2014.

LDB: Lei de diretrizes e bases da educação nacional. Brasília: Senado Federal, Coordenação de Edições Técnicas, 2017. 58 p.

MORGAN, Gareth. Imagens da organização. São Paulo: Atlas, 1996.

Plano Nacional de Educação 2014-2024: Lei nº 13.005, de 25 de junho de 2014, que aprova o Plano Nacional de Educação (PNE) e dá outras providências. Brasília: Câmara dos Deputados, Edições Câmara – Série legislação; n. 125, 2014. 86 p.

VAZ, José Carlos. Processos de trabalho no setor público: gestão e redesenho. 2008. Disponível em: <<http://www.camaraitapevi.sp.gov.br/images/PDF/gactexto5.pdf>>. Acesso em 14 de novembro de 2018.

SILVEIRA, Jader Luís da. A Universidade como cérebro para gestores: Educação Superior e Autonomia Universitária. P@RTES (São Paulo), ISSN 1678-8419. n.0, v. 1, p.1., 2019.